

CHORD: Ptolemy's table of chords

Dietmar G. Schrausser

Karl-Franzens University, Graz, Austria

Overview

CHORD Application¹ for Android (Schrausser, 2023): Famous table of chord lengths according to Ptolemy's *Almagest* (1515, fol. 7r ff.) converted into decimal values and calculated in comparison using the sine function, see Halma (1813, p. 38 ff.), Heiberg (1898, p. 48 ff.) or Toomer (1984, p. 57 ff., 1998, res.).

Chord lengths l_0 are calculated according to *Ptolemy's theorem* (figure 1) within the relation between four sides and two diagonals of a cyclic quadrilateral where

$$AC \cdot BD = AB \cdot CD + BC \cdot AD.$$

Figure 1: Cyclic quadrilateral with chord length representation.

Chord lengths l_0 (figure 1) are expressed in fractional parts of sexagesimal numerals $x y z$. Decimal values l_1 are calculated as

$$l_1 = x + y/60 + z/60^2.$$

Sixtieths is the average interpolation number to be added to length l_0 or l_1 each time angle increases by one minute of arc, that is $n = 30$ times per half angle degree α .

Lengths l_2 to given arcus α and diameter d are calculated using the sine function where

$$l_2 = d \cdot \sin(\alpha \cdot \pi / 360).$$

This is equivalent in terms of content to distance s or radius r determination via angular diameter V with

$$r = s \cdot \tan(V/2).$$

¹ <https://github.com/Schrausser/Ptolemy-s-table-of-chords>

In the absence of trigonometric sine functions, however, no *calculation* was made with distance parameters s , but tabularized values from previous model calculations with given $d = 120$ by means of the *Pythagorean theorem*

$$a^2 + b^2 = c^2$$

were used and interpolated to the corresponding angle values of expansion:

Figure 2: Screenshots from CHORD Application.

Chord parameters $l_{(120)}$ can then be adapted to empirical $l_{(d)}$ proportions by transforming the model parameter with

$$l_{(d)} = l_{(120)} \cdot d / 120.$$

Chord length values $l_{(e)}$ corresponding to *empirical* distances s can be expressed by multiplying $l_{(d)}$ with a ratio factor δ as $l_{(e)} = l_{(d)} \cdot \delta$ to given angle α , where according to *Pythagoras*

$$\delta = s \cdot [(d/2)^2 - (l/2)^2]^{-1/2}.$$

Differences *diff* show the difference between (1) *sixtieth* and arithmetical interpolation as well as the difference between (2) the calculation types of chord lengths l_1 and l_2 , see *chords.md* or *chords.xlsx* tables.

Using this method along with methods for parallax determination, Ptolemy was able to determine e.g. Moon's distance ($d = 59$ Earth radii, er) and radius ($r = 0.29 er$, where $er = 6378 km$) quite accurate, see e.g. Goldstein (1967).


```

DIM dlg$(6)
dlg$(1)=smq$+" Mode: "+mode$
dlg$(2)=smq$+" d="+STR$(ROUND(d,3))
dlg$(3)=smq$+" arc "+_ga$+"="+STR$(ROUND(arc,3))+""
dlg$(4)=smq$+" s="+STR$(ROUND(s_,3))
dlg$(5)="Ok"
dlg$(6)="_ex$+" Exit"
ENDIF
IF m_sw=-1 % // Free rotate mode //
DIM dlg$(3)
dlg$(1)=smq$+" Mode: "+mode$
dlg$(2)="Ok"
dlg$(3)="_ex$+" Exit"
ENDIF
DIALOG.SELECT dlg, dlg$[],_name$+" Ptolemy's Chord Lengths "+_ver$+" - Options:"
IF dlg=1
m_sw=m_sw*-1
IF m_sw=1: mode$="Calculate"
ELSE:mode$="Free Rotation":ENDIF
ENDIF
IF m_sw=1
IF dlg=2
INPUT "Parameter d=...",d,120
d=ABS(d)
IF d<0.01 THEN d=0.01
IF d>9999999 THEN d=9999999
ENDIF
IF dlg=3
INPUT "Angle arc "+_ga$+"=..."",arc,90
arc=ABS(arc)
IF arc<0.001 THEN arc=0.001
IF arc>180 THEN arc=180
ENDIF
IF dlg=4
INPUT "Distance s=...",s_,s_
s_=ABS(s_)
IF s_<0.001 THEN s_=0.001
IF s_>9999999 THEN s_=9999999
d=s_/COS(TORADIANS(arc)/2)
d=ABS(2*d)
ENDIF
IF dlg=5: st1=1:ENDIF
IF dlg=6: GOSUB fin:END:ENDIF
ENDIF
IF m_sw=-1
IF dlg=2: st1=1:ENDIF
IF dlg=3: GOSUB fin:END:ENDIF
ENDIF
UNTIL st1
! // //
RETURN
textout:
GR.TEXT.SIZE sx/25
GR.COLOR 255,0,0,0,1
GR.TEXT.ALIGN 3
GR.TEXT.DRAW txt,sx-sx/20,sy/20,"d: "+STR$(ROUND(r*2,3))
GR.COLOR 255,255,0,0,1
GR.TEXT.ALIGN 2
GR.TEXT.DRAW txt,mx,sy-sy/20,"Ptolemy's Chord Lengths"
GR.TEXT.SIZE sx/30
GR.COLOR 255,255,150,0,1
GR.TEXT.ALIGN 1
GR.TEXT.DRAW txt,sx/20,sy/20,"a: "+STR$(ROUND(a*r,3))+"" b: "+STR$(ROUND(-b*r,3))
GR.COLOR 255,0,200,0,1
GR.TEXT.ALIGN 3
GR.TEXT.DRAW txt,sx-sx/20,sy/8,"s: "+STR$(ROUND(ABS(s1*r),3)) % // s //
GR.COLOR 255,255,0,0,1
GR.TEXT.ALIGN 2
GR.TEXT.DRAW txt,mx,sy/8,"chord 1: "+STR$(ROUND(c*r,3))
GR.TEXT.SIZE sx/25
GR.TEXT.DRAW txt,mx,sy/8+sy/20,hex$

```

```

GR.TEXT.SIZE sx/30
GR.COLOR 255,0,0,255,1
GR.TEXT.DRAW txt,mx,sy-sy/5,"arc "+_ga$+": "+STR$(ROUND(arc,3))+""
RETURN
! // //
freerotcalc:
c0=SQR((tx-mx)^2+(ty-my)^2) % // Lengths //
c1=mx/c0 % // Ratio to radius (mx length) //
tx=mx+(tx-mx)*c1 % // tx to length for radius //
ty=my+(ty-my)*c1 % // ty to length for radius //
a=mx-(tx-mx)
b=ty-my
a=a/mx
b=b/mx
! // //
c=SQR(a^2+b^2) % // Chord length l //
s1=SQR(r^2-((c*r)/2)^2) % // Distance s //
s1=s1/r:IF arc>180 THEN s1=-s1 % // //
ah=INT(c*r) % // Hex values //
bh=60*(c*r-ah) % // //
b1h=INT(bh) % // //
ch=60*(bh-b1h) % // //
! // //
hex$=INT$(ah)+" "+INT$(bh)+" "+STR$(ROUND(ch,1))
arc=TODEGREES(ASIN(-b)) % // Angle arc //
IF a>1: arc=(90-arc)+90:ENDIF % // //
IF arc<0:arc=360+arc:ENDIF % // //
RETURN
! //
fin:
PRINT_name$+" Ptolemy's Chord Lengths "+_ver$
PRINT"Copyright "+_cr$+" 2023 by Dietmar Gerald Schrausser"
PRINT "https://github.com/Schrausser/Ptolemy-s-table-of-chords"
PRINT "DOI:10.5281/zenodo.7948117"
RETURN
! // END //
! //

```

References

- Goldstein, B. R. (1967). The Arabic Version of Ptolemy's Planetary Hypotheses. *Transactions of the American Philosophical Society*, 57(4), 3–55.
<https://doi.org/10.2307/1006040>
- Halma, N. (1813). *Composition mathématique de Claude Ptolémée*. Traduite pour la première fois du grec en français, sur les manuscrits originaux de la Bibliothèque Impériale de Paris, par M. Halma; et suivie des notes de M. Delambre, ... A Paris, chez Henri Grand, libraire, Rue Saint-André-des-Arcs, N° 51. (Mathematical composition of Claude Ptolemy. Translated for the first time from Greek into French, on the Original Manuscripts of the Imperial Library of Paris...)
<https://ia600202.us.archive.org/12/items/>
- Heiberg, J. L. (1898). *Claudii Ptolemaei Opera quae exstant omnia. Syntaxis Mathematica. Vol. 1. 1*. Lipsae: In aedibus B. G. Teubneri.
<https://archive.org/details/pt1claudiptolemaei01ptoluoft>
- Ptolemaeus, C. (1515). *Almagestum CL. Ptolemei Pheludiensis Alexandrini astronomorum principis: Opus ingens ac nobile omnes Caelorum motus continens*. Felicibus astris eat in lucem: Ductu Petri Liechtenstein Coloniensis Germani. Anno Virginei Partus, 1515, Die 10. Ia. Venetiis ex officina eiusdem litteraria. (Almagest of CL. Ptolemy Pheludiens, head of the Alexandrian astronomers: A great and noble work containing all the movements of the heavens...) <https://doi.org/10.3931/e-rara-206>
- Schrausser, D. G. (2023). *Schrausser/Ptolemy-s-table-of-chords: Calculator (v3.5.0)*. Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7948117>
- Toomer, G. J. (1984). *Ptolemy's Almagest*. Duckworth, London & Springer, New York.
<https://www.cambridge.org/core/journals/journal-of-hellenic-studies/article/>
- . (1998). *Ptolemy's Almagest. Revised*. Princeton, NJ: Princeton University Press.
<https://www.amazon.de/Ptolemys-Almagest-Ptolemy/dp/0691002606>